

A Quantitative Approach to Stability Correlations of Some Lanthanide-Edta-Hydroxy Acid Ternary Complexes

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Manuscript received 16 March 1984, accepted 15 August 1984

Metal-ligand stability constants of the mixed-ligand complexes of lanthanide metal ions, viz. La^{III} , Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} with edta as primary ligand and malic (ma), lactic (la), glycolic (ga), or gluconic (gluc) acid as secondary ligand have been determined pH-metrically at 25° and ionic strength of 0.2 (mol dm^{-3} NaClO_4), using Irving-Rossotti titration technique. The ternary systems are of the type, $\text{M} + \text{A} \rightleftharpoons \text{MA}$, $\text{MA} + \text{L} \rightleftharpoons \text{MAL}$. The $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values have been found to lie in the sequence $\text{La}^{III} < \text{Ce}^{III} < \text{Pr}^{III} < \text{Nd}^{III} < \text{Sm}^{III}$ with respect to metal ions, and $\text{ma} > \text{la} > \text{ga} > \text{gluc}$ with respect to the secondary ligands. The $\Delta \log K$ values are negative due to electrostatic effects. Six log-log type stability correlations have been discussed with the help of mathematical equations derived for the purpose. It has been found that the plots of (i) $\log K_{ML}^{MA}$ vs $\log K_{HL}^H$, (ii) $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs $\log K_{HL}^H$, (iii) $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs $\log K_{MA}^M$, (iv) $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs $\log K_{ML}^M$, (v) $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs $\log K_{MAL}^M$, and (vi) $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs $\log K_{M'AL}^M$, are all linear with non-unit slopes.

CORRELATIONS between the stability constants of binary metallic complexes and the properties of metal ions and ligands have been discussed at length¹⁻⁴. A linear relationship exists^{5,6} between the basicity of secondary ligands and the stability constants of mixed-ligand complexes of the type (M-dipy-L). Some aspects of structure and stability of ternary complexes have recently been reviewed⁷. Correlations between the stability constants of ternary lanthanide complexes with some fundamental properties of the metal ions and ligand characteristics have been reported by us⁸.

The present communication deals with a quantitative study of some log-log type correlations amongst the stability constants of the mixed complexes of La^{III} , Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} (LN=lanthanide) using edta as primary ligand and aliphatic hydroxy acids, malic (ma), lactic (la), glycolic (ga), or gluconic (gluc) as secondary ligands.

Experimental

Standard solutions of metal ions and edta were prepared as reported earlier by us⁸.

The solutions of ma, la, ga and gluc were prepared in double-distilled water. The formation constants of the mixed complexes have been determined by using Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique⁹ and its extension to ternary systems¹⁰. Usual titration sets for 1:1 binary and 1:1:1 ternary complexes were prepared keeping the ionic strength constant at 0.2 (mol dm^{-3} NaClO_4) and titrated against 0.2 mol dm^{-3} carbonate-free sodium hydroxide at 25°. The pH values of the solutions were recorded on an Elico LI-120 digital pH

meter. A representative set of plots of pH vs ml of alkali for (La-edta-ma) system has been shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Representative pH-titration plots for 1:1 binary and 1:1:1 ternary La^{3+} -edta-ma: Systems: a=acid, L=ma, MA=LN-edta, ML=LN-ma, MAL=La-edta-ma, T=composite curve.

Results and Discussion

The metal-ligand stability constants of the ternary complexes ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$) along with other

TABLE 1—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 1 : 1 : 1 TERNARY COMPLEXES AND OTHER RELATED PROPERTIES

I = 0.2 (mol dm ⁻³ NaClO ₄)		Temp. = 25°				
Secondary ligand	Property	La ^{III}	Ce ^{III}	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}
Malic acid (ma)	log K _{MAL} ^{MA}	3.38	3.46	3.53	3.75	4.11
	-Δ log K	0.37	0.55	0.67	0.70	0.42
	-ΔG(kJ mol ⁻¹)	16.44	16.87	17.19	18.24	20.04
	log K _s	9.59	9.87	10.16	10.51	10.77
	-(%) R.S.	9.80	13.71	15.95	15.73	9.27
	(%) R.A.	64.75	64.90	65.25	64.31	61.83
Lactic acid (la)	log K _{MAL} ^{MA}	3.35	3.43	3.55	3.68	3.86
	-Δ log K	0.33	0.31	0.43	0.31	0.26
	-ΔG(kJ mol ⁻¹)	16.31	16.69	17.30	17.99	18.82
	log K _s	9.57	9.81	10.11	10.40	10.67
	-(%) R.S.	8.96	8.29	10.80	7.77	6.31
	(%) R.A.	64.99	65.03	64.88	64.62	63.82
Glycolic acid (ga)	log K _{MAL} ^{MA}	3.28	3.47	3.55	3.64	3.72
	-Δ log K	0.32	0.16	0.13	0.19	0.20
	-ΔG(kJ mol ⁻¹)	16.03	16.87	17.44	17.59	18.13
	log K _s	9.55	9.76	10.04	10.36	10.62
	-(%) R.S.	8.88	4.40	3.50	4.96	5.10
	(%) R.A.	65.65	64.44	64.3	64.86	64.97
Gluconic acid (gluc)	log K _{MAL} ^{MA}	2.13	2.46	2.69	2.86	2.92
	-Δ log K	0.86	0.70	0.57	0.60	0.62
	-ΔG(kJ mol ⁻¹)	10.37	11.96	13.11	13.63	14.23
	log K _s	9.39	9.68	9.93	10.25	10.52
	-(%) R.S.	28.00	22.15	17.48	17.60	17.51
	(%) R.A.	77.31	74.58	72.19	72.09	72.24

related values, viz. ΔG ($\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$), $\Delta \log K$, $\log K_s$, (%) R.S. and (%) R.A. (terms explained latter) of the ternary complexes have been recorded in Table 1.

The pH-titration plots in Fig. 1 indicate that the ternary systems under study are of the type $M + A \rightleftharpoons MA$, $MA + L \rightleftharpoons MAL$, where the secondary ligand L combines with MA (a stable primary complex whose pH of formation is much below the pH of formation of mixed complexes) to form a mixed complex MAL. The much stronger complexing tendency of edta eliminates the possibility of any ligand displacement of the type $MA + L \rightleftharpoons ML + A$. Also, the hexadentate nature of edta minimises the possibility of formation of species MA_2 or the disproportionation of MAL into MA_2 or ML_2 ¹¹. The formation of mixed complexes has been confirmed by the non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve¹² on the experimental mixed complex curve. The formation of mixed complexes takes place at the pH where the formation of hydroxo species can be ignored. The plots of $\bar{n}/[L]$ vs $[L]$ (Fig. not shown) have been found to be smooth, indicating the absence of any protonated or polynuclear species.

The general order of stability for the complexes has been found to be $\log K_{MA}^{MA} \gg \log K_{ML}^{ML} > \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$. The lower values of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ than $\log K_{ML}^{ML}$ may be due to coulombic repulsion between the negatively charged primary complex $(LN-edta)^-$ and the incoming secondary ligand L^- or L^{2-}

during the formation of ternary complexes. The $\Delta \log K$ values are consequently negative.

The $\Delta \log K$ values measure the relative ease or difficulty in the formation of mixed-ligand complex MAL as compared to ML. The magnitude of $\Delta \log K$ cannot, however, be compared for different mixed complexes as its value depends on the $\log K_{ML}^{ML}$ value. A parameter 'Relative Stabilisation' (R.S.) for the ternary complex may be defined as,

$$(\%) \text{ R.S.} = [(\log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^{ML}) / \log K_{ML}^{ML}] \times 100.$$

The values of (%) R.S. may be compared for the mixed-ligand complexes to estimate their relative stabilisation at a certain temperature. In the present case the numerical values of (%) R.S. lie in the range 9.27-15.95 for ma, 6.31-10.80 for la, 3.50-8.88 for ga and 17.48-28.0 for gluc. It seems that, as pointed out by Grenthe¹³ for binary complexes of la and ga on the basis of thermodynamic parameters, the bonding between lanthanide metal ion and hydroxyl group takes place *via* a water molecule through hydrogen bonding rather than a direct LN-O bond being formed with the hydroxyl group.

The values of statistical stability constant¹⁴ ($\log K_s$) have also been calculated for the present set of complexes, assuming lanthanide metal ion as octacoordinate, edta as hexadentate and secondary ligand as bidentate. The calculated $\log K_s$ values are found to be greater than $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values which explains the involvement of astatistical factors

(mainly electrostatic) during the formation of mixed complexes.

Another new parameter '(%) Relative Astatisticality' (R.A.) of the ternary complex may be defined as,

$$(\%) \text{ R.A.} = [\log K_s - \log K_{MAL}^M] / \log K_s \times 100.$$

The numerical values of (%) R.A. may be used for a quantitative estimation of the relative astatisticality involved in the formation of the ternary complexes at a certain temperature. The values of (%) R.A. in the present case are found to vary between 61 to 65% for ma, la and ga, and about 72 to 77% for gluc mixed complexes.

The sequence of $\log K_{MAL}^M$ values with respect to the secondary ligands has been found to be $ma > la > ga > gluc$, which is the order of their basicity. Similar results are reported in for the (LN-cdta.L) chelates¹² (where, LN=La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, L=ma, la, ga). The lower values of stability for the gluc ternary systems may be due to greater steric hindrance involved in its case. Of the secondary ligands in the present case, ga and la are closely related. Substitution of additional methyl group in la should cause a lowering in the stability of the resulting ternary complexes, but the observed sequence is reverse, i.e. $la > ga$, which is in good agreement with the values of similar ternary complexes reported^{12,14}. This may be due to a cooperative effect between the primary and secondary ligands (la) in the ternary systems.

The stability sequence with respect to metal ions has been found to be $La^{III} < Ce^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Sm^{III}$, which is the order of increasing ionic potentials of these metal ions. It is interesting to note that the metal ions under study have almost identical electronegativities. On going from La^{III} to Sm^{III} the ionic radii, the sum of the first three ionisation potentials and their polarising powers vary by 7.5% (decrease), 11.6% (increase) and 16.6% (increase), respectively. The increase in $\log K_{MAL}^M$ values is about 21% for ma, 15% for la, 13% for ga, and as much as 37% for gluc. It is evident that apart from the above metal characteristics, these ligands cause varying degrees of stabilisation in the ternary systems.

Stability correlations (log-log type): Some log-log type stability correlations have been discussed adopting a mathematical approach. The expressions correlating the two stability constants have been derived by combining the relationships involving free energy changes during the formations of HL, ML and MAL and the relationships of the type, $\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K$. Equations (1) and (2) have been derived at standard conditions.

$$\log K_{ML}^M = \log K_{HL}^H + (2.303 RT)^{-1} \cdot [(G_M^O - G_H^O) + (G_{HL}^O - G_{ML}^O)] \quad (1)$$

$$\log K_{MAL}^M = \log K_{HL}^H + (2.303 RT)^{-1} \cdot [(G_{MA}^O - G_H^O) + (G_{HL}^O - G_{MAL}^O)] \quad (2)$$

It is obvious from equations (1) and (2) that a plot of $\log K_{ML}^M$ vs $\log K_{HL}^H$ or $\log K_{MAL}^M$ vs $\log K_{HL}^H$ will be linear if the first term within brackets on the right hand side is constant, and the second term is either negligible in comparison to the first term, or a constant, or a linear function of $\log K_{HL}^H$. The first two conditions will lead to a plot of unit slope, the third to a non-unit slope. For a given metal ion the quantity $(G_M^O - G_H^O)$ in equation (1) and for a given primary complex the quantity $(G_{MA}^O - G_H^O)$ in equation (2) will be constant. The log-log plots, $\log K_{ML}^M$ vs $\log K_{HL}^H$, and $\log K_{MAL}^M$ vs $\log K_{HL}^H$ for the various systems under study are shown in Figs. 2(a) and

Fig. 2. Log-Log plots of (a) $\log K_{ML}^M$ vs $\log K_{HL}^H$ (o) and (b) $\log K_{MAL}^M$ vs $\log K_{HL}^H$.

2(b) respectively. The slope values (Table 2) are all non-unity in both the cases showing the existence of the third possibility in these systems.

Four more equations. (3) to (6) have also been derived.

$$\log K_{MAL}^M = \log K_{MA}^M + (2.303 RT)^{-1} \cdot [(G_L^O - G_M^O) - (G_{MA}^O - 2G_{MAL}^O + G_{MAL}^O)] \quad (3)$$

$$\log K_{MAL}^M = \log K_{ML}^M + (2.303 RT)^{-1} \cdot [(G_{MA}^O - G_M^O) + [(G_{ML}^O - G_{MAL}^O) - G_{MAL}^O]] \quad (4)$$

$$\log K_{MAL}^M = \log K_{MAL}^M + (2.303 RT)^{-1} \cdot [(G_L^O - G_M^O) - (G_{MAL}^O - G_{MAL}^O)] \quad (5)$$

$$\log K_{MAL}^M = \log K_{M'AL}^M + (2.303 RT)^{-1} \cdot [(G_{MA}^O - G_{M'AL}^O) - (G_{MAL}^O - G_{M'AL}^O)] \quad (6)$$

The first term in equations (3), (4) and (5) will be constant for a given set of ligands (permitting variation of metal ion), metal and primary ligand (permitting variation of secondary ligand), and closely related secondary ligands (permitting variation of metal ions for the same pair of secondary ligands), respectively.

The plots corresponding to equations (3), (4) and (5) have been shown in Figs. 3a, 3b and 3c, respectively. They are all linear. The slope values are given in Table 2. This again indicates that the second term within brackets on the right hand side in each case is a linear function of the corresponding first term on the right hand side as the slope values are non-unity. The literature values of $\log K_{MAL}^M$ for the systems of the type (LN-cdta-L)¹² have been used with our $\log K_{ML}^M$ values under comparable

TABLE 2—SLOPE VALUES FOR LINEAR PLOTS REPRESENTING LOG-LOG TYPE CORRELATIONS

Correlation*	Slope values				
	La ^{III}	Ce ^{III}	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}
log K_{ML}^M vs log K_{HL}^H (eq. 1)	0.15	0.38	0.49	0.62	0.61
log K_{MAL}^{MA} vs log K_{HL}^H (eq. 2)	0.40	—	0.40	0.11	0.39
		ma	la	ga	gluc
log K_{MAL}^{MA} vs log K_{MA}^M (eq. 3)		0.55	0.39	0.33	0.56
log K_{MAL}^{MA} vs log K_{ML}^M (eq. 4)		0.93	1.15	1.32	1.36
		EDTA			
		CDTA			
		1.18	1.93	0.93**	
log K_{MAL}^{MA} vs log $K_{M'A}^{M'A}$ (eq. 6)		1.75	1.30	0.69	0.68
log K_{MAL}^{MA} vs log $K_{M'AL}^{M'AL}$ (eq. 5)			0.86		

* L - la, L' - ga, ** Ref. 15.

conditions, for studying the log-log correlation represented by equation (4). The plots are linear (Fig. 3c). The slope values are mentioned in the Table 2 for comparison.

Fig. 3. Log-Log plots for (a) $\text{Log } K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs $\text{Log } K_{MA}^M$, (b) $\text{Log } K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs $\text{Log } K_{ML}^M$, (c) $\text{Log } K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs $\text{Log } K_{M'A}^{M'A}$, (L - la, L' - ga), (d) $\text{Log } K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs $\text{Log } K_{M'AL}^{M'AL}$.

In equation (6), however, the first term within brackets on the right hand side, *i.e.* ($G_{MA}^0 - G_{M'A}^0$) may vary with metal ions. The plots $\text{log } K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs $\text{log } K_{M'AL}^{M'AL}$ (Fig. 3d) are linear indicating that for the present set of metal ions this term remains rather constant.

Table 2 shows the slope values obtained for various log-log type correlations of the present study.

The deviations from linearity may be ascribed to considerations of enthalpy and/or entropy¹⁹. It is reported for some binary complexes that the slope values for the correlations between $\text{log } K_{ML}^M$ and $\text{log } K_{HL}^H$ (or $\text{log } \beta_{H_n,z}^H$) depend on (i) ionisation potentials of the metal ions¹⁹, (ii) nuclear repulsions between the metal ion and donor atom²⁰, or (iii) the polarisation of the ligand by metal ions²¹. A large number of suitably planned ternary systems will have to be studied before any generalisation may be possible.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. Y. G. Kher, Head, Department of Chemistry for providing facilities. Thanks are also due to the M.P. Council of Science and Technology, Bhopal for a research grant (M.C.S.) and to the U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship (S.N.L.).

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